

Impact of Cochlear Coiling Morphology on Bone-Conducted Sound in the Human: A Computational Model Approach

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Abstract. The perception of bone-conducted sound in human hearing involves complex pathways where vibrations on the surface of the skull stimulate sensory cells in the cochlea. One such pathway, termed compressional bone conduction, entails vibrations of the bone surrounding the inner ear, leading to alterations in the cochlear space and fluid flow between cochlear ducts and the oval and round windows. Evolutionary perspectives suggest that the human ear structures may have adapted to minimize the impact of self-generated body sounds, such as breathing, chewing, or vocalization. One notable feature believed to contribute to this adaptation is the coiling of the cochlea, hypothesized to be less sensitive to internally generated sounds than a straight cochlea. To explore the effect of cochlear shape on bone-conducted sound perception, a computational model simulating bone conduction stimulation in humans was developed. Two models were created, one with 2.5 turns of coiled cochlear ducts and another with a straight cochlea. Both models represented scala vestibuli and scala tympani as half-elliptic cross-sectional areas with linear tapering from the basal part to the helicotrema at the apical end. Longitudinal wave stimulation with a constant speed of 400 m/s was applied.

Simulation results revealed that a straight cochlea exhibited approximately 9 dB greater compressional stimulation at 100 Hz, decreasing with frequency and reaching 7 dB less compressional stimulation at 10 kHz compared to a coiled cochlea. However, despite the influence of cochlear coiling on compressional response, the total bone-conducted response differed by only 2 dB between the two models. Other factors, aside from compression, dominated the overall response in bone conduction hearing. Consequently, this study suggests that the coiling shape of the cochlea may not significantly minimize the perception of self-generated sounds compared to a coiled cochlea in the context of bone-conducted hearing.

INTRODUCTION

The ear's ability to detect environmental sounds has evolved through natural selection, utilizing various anatomical structures that facilitate this process (1). These structures include the outer ear, which enhances sound pressure at mid-frequencies through resonance in the ear canal; the middle ear ossicles, which convert airborne sounds into fluid-borne vibrations; and the sensory cells in the inner ear, which amplify weak sounds. Moreover, evidence suggests that the ear has evolved mechanisms to reduce unwanted noise (2,3), particularly internal noise transmitted through bone conduction (BC 4,5). Therefore, the ear may be specialized to enhance external sounds transmitted through air conduction (AC) while insensitive to internally generated sounds transmitted through BC.

Building upon this premise, Barany (6) proposed that the middle ear ossicles minimize the impact of BC stimulation by strategically distributing mass. This idea was supported by von Békésy (7), who observed that the ossicles' mass distribution minimizes inertial forces during BC vibration, particularly when the center of mass is aligned with the rotational axis. Consequently, the inertial forces acting on the ossicles during BC-induced middle ear vibration are diminished compared to what would occur if the mass were aligned with the ossicles' vibration direction. Vibration measurements conducted during BC stimulation revealed that augmenting ossicle mass by 100 mg at the umbo amplifies stapes motion by 10 to 20 dB at frequencies below 1 kHz and approximately 5 dB at frequencies exceeding 4 kHz (8). However, it is noteworthy that other stimulation pathways, aside from middle ear inertia,

contribute as much or more to BC hearing (9-11). Consequently, an increase in relative ossicle vibration does not necessarily translate to improved perception of BC sound.

The coiling of the cochlea in mammalian ears has been suggested as a mechanism to mitigate the impact of bone conduction (BC) sound. The rationale is that an uncoiled cochlea might exhibit greater sensitivity to BC sounds compared to a coiled one. However, when considering BC sound perception, multiple contributing pathways have been identified (4,10,12). In humans, five such pathways have been deemed significant, with varying dominance across different frequency ranges (4,10,13).

In addition to the cochlea, factors such as sound pressure in the ear canal (11,14), inertial effects of the middle ear ossicles (8,15), and sound pressure transmission from the cranial space (16) have been recognized as potential contributors of BC sound in the human. The two BC pathways that influence the cochlea directly are inertial effects of the cochlear fluids and compression and expansion of the cochlear space (17). Of these, fluid inertia is typically assumed to be incompressible and requires compliant inlets and outlets to function properly. The oval and round windows, along with the vestibular and cochlear aqueducts, are prominent examples of such inlets and outlets. As a result, fluid inertia is presumed to be primarily influenced by the basal portion of the cochlea and thus remains largely unaffected by its coiling.

On the other hand, the compression and expansion of the cochlea are influenced by factors such as wave type and speed in the skull bone surrounding the inner ear, as well as potentially by the geometry and orientation of the cochlea itself (17,18). Consequently, while cochlear coiling may impact the compression and expansion pathway for BC hearing, its effect on other pathways is considered negligible.

The aim of this study is to investigate how cochlear coiling influences the perception of BC sound in humans. This is accomplished by first examining the impact of cochlear coiling on the compression and expansion pathway for BC sound. Subsequently, its effect on overall BC perception is analyzed, considering the interplay of five factors contributing to BC hearing in humans. To achieve this, a lumped-element model specifically designed for simulating BC stimulation in humans is used (9,10,17).

THE MODEL

The simulations utilize a model based on computational frameworks developed by the author for BC stimulation in humans (9,10,17). Figure 1 illustrates the current model, depicting impedances and generators employed to simulate fluid flow during both AC and BC stimulation. While detailed information and values for each impedance and generator are available in previous work (17), our focus here is on the specifics pertinent to investigating the impact of cochlear coiling.

In Fig. 1, the various BC pathways affect the generators differently. The generator U_{SF} represents the volume velocity resulting from stapes footplate motion in the oval window. This generator operates when the stimulation pathway involves either sound pressure in the ear canal (for both AC and BC) or ossicle motion due to middle ear inertia. The sound pressure generator P_{IC_VA} represents the sound pressure external to the vestibular aqueduct in the cranial cavity, representing the transmission pathway of sound pressure within the cerebrospinal fluid surrounding the brain. Three pressure generators located within the inner ear (P_V , P_{SV} , and P_{ST}) are driven by the inertial effects of inner ear fluids. Finally, the volume velocity generators U_V , U_{SV} , and U_{ST} represent fluid flow within the inner ear resulting from alterations of inner ear volume during bony vibrations.

In this study, the mechanism underlying hearing perception is presumed to be driven by volume velocity through impedance Z_C , primarily constituted by the impedance of the basilar membrane. This mechanism mirrors the fluid flow between the scala vestibuli and scala tympani at the basal cochlear end. Absolute data is not presented herein; instead, relative changes in volume velocity through Z_C serve as indicators of the effects between coiled and uncoiled cochleae.

To evaluate the impact of cochlear coiling, the motion of the bone surrounding the inner ear is examined. This analysis assumes that the bony wave motion within the skull base is longitudinal, with a wave speed of 400 m/s, based on experimental measurements of human skull bone vibrations (19). Considering the short distances in the model, the amplitude of bony wave motion remains constant, and only phase differences due to the wave speed are utilized to compute the motion of each compartment in the model. For simplicity, the wave motion is assumed to be one-dimensional.

In the cochlea, fluid inertia is confined to the basal portion where fluid exchange occurs between the oval and round windows (represented by P_{SV} and P_{ST} in Fig. 1). This aspect remains constant for both coiled and uncoiled

RESULTS

The simulation results of the five components influencing BC hearing are presented in Fig. 3. Fig. 3A illustrates the results with a coiled cochlea, while Fig. 3B depicts the results for an uncoiled cochlea. Fig. 3A mirrors the findings reported in Stenfelt et al. (10), as the models employed are identical. In Fig. 3, the total sum of the components is normalized to 0 dB, and the graphs represent the relative importance of the different components for BC sound perception. According to these computations, fluid inertia significantly influences BC perception across the presented frequency range (0.1 to 10 kHz), with contributions from other components observed at specific frequency bands.

The transmission of sound pressure within the cranial cavity appears influential at lower frequencies but diminishes above 500 Hz. Middle-ear inertia emerges as significant at 1 kHz and dominates BC perception between 1 and 2 kHz, with substantial contributions persisting at higher frequencies. Cochlear compression contributes comparably to other components at frequencies between 300 and 500 Hz and at the highest frequencies but exhibits lower levels (10 to 30 dB) compared to other contributors elsewhere in the frequency spectrum. The influence of cochlear compression undergoes alteration with cochlear uncoiling (Fig. 3B), wherein its contribution increases at frequencies below 2 kHz but decreases at higher frequencies. In this model, the contribution from ear canal sound pressure is lower compared to other components, except for sound pressure from the cranial cavity, which exhibits the least influence at frequencies above 1 kHz.

FIGURE 3. A) The relative contribution from the 5 different contributors to BC hearing when the cochlea is coiled. B) The relative contribution from the 5 different contributors to BC hearing when the cochlea is uncoiled.

Figure 4 depicts the impact of cochlear uncoiling on hearing sensitivity. Fig. 4A reveals that cochlear coiling has no discernible effect on cochlear response during AC stimulation. Consequently, the model suggests that in terms of fluid flow over the basal part of the basilar membrane, there is no difference in the AC response between coiled and uncoiled cochleae. Upon examination of Fig. 3, no indication of the impact of cochlear coiling on any of the BC components is evident, except for the compression component. Therefore, Fig. 4B specifically illustrates the effect of cochlear uncoiling on the compression component alone, as well as for all BC components summed together. This analysis reveals that uncoiling the cochlea enhances the BC response from compression by 4 to 9 dB at frequencies below 2 kHz. Conversely, at higher frequencies, there is a reduction in the compression response, reaching -7 dB at 10 kHz.

Given that other components contributing to BC hearing are overall more significant than cochlear compression, minor differences in BC sensitivity due to uncoiling are observed. These differences are limited to within ± 2 dB, with a slight improvement noted at frequencies around 300 Hz and a decrease observed at the highest frequencies analyzed. Considering the small overall differences, it can be concluded, based on the current model simulations, that uncoiling of the cochlea has a minor effect on BC sensitivity.

FIGURE 4. A) The sensitivity change of uncoiling the cochlea when the stimulation is a sound pressure in the ear canal (AC). B) The effect of uncoiling the cochlea when stimulation is a BC vibration at the mastoid. The effect on cochlear compression alone is shown with a red line and the overall change in BC sensitivity is shown by the blue line.

DISCUSSION

The objective of this study was to investigate whether the coiling of the cochlea affects the perception of BC sound. This inquiry stems from the hypothesis that cochlear coiling may have evolved to mitigate the influence of internally generated body sounds (such as one's own voice, chewing, and breathing) transmitted through bone conduction. Model simulations conducted here suggest that there is minimal difference in BC sensitivity between cochleae with varying degrees of coiling. Thus, it is improbable that cochlear coiling evolved primarily to reduce the impact of BC sound. Rather, it is more likely that cochlear coiling serves to accommodate the elongated hearing organs necessary for detecting a wide range of frequencies with high resolution (1).

The notion that the distribution of mass in the middle ear ossicles evolved primarily to mitigate the effects of BC sound finds limited support in this study. Previous research by Stenfelt et al. (8) indicates that an increase in ossicle mass at the umbo (the point where the ossicles attach to the eardrum) results in a 10 to 20 dB elevation in ossicle vibration levels at frequencies below 1 kHz, attributed to a lowering of the resonance frequency of the ossicles. However, as shown in Fig. 3, the impact of middle ear inertia on BC sound is 10 to 20 dB lower compared to other contributing factors. Therefore, a significant increase in ossicle mass would not substantially enhance BC sensitivity in humans. Consequently, the distribution of mass in the ossicles may not primarily serve to attenuate BC sound but rather to optimize the transmission of AC sounds through the middle ear.

It is important to acknowledge that there are instances where changes in the mass distribution of the middle ear ossicles do enhance low-frequency BC hearing. For instance, studies have demonstrated that the malleus of the golden mole possesses excessive mass, leading to speculation that it utilizes this trait to detect seismic vibrations through BC hearing (21,22).

The discovery that cochlear curvature does not affect the response to AC sound (as depicted in Fig. 4A) contradicts experimental and computational findings reported in existing literature (23). However, it is crucial to note that the model utilized in the current analysis focuses on fluid flow at the basal portion of the basilar membrane as the primary auditory excitation, while disregarding the effects of the traveling wave toward the basal end. Consequently, this model overlooks the influence of cochlear curvature on the transmission of low-frequency waves within the cochlea. Nonetheless, even if such an effect were considered, it would impact both AC and BC hearing equally, thus not supporting the argument that cochlear coiling evolved primarily to reduce BC sound.

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[Geoff Manly] I would like to make two very brief comments. One is that the evolution of the cochlea and the middle ear is not a very simple process. And, during the period when the cochlea was gradually coiling during evolution, the middle ear in most mammals were still connected to the lower jaw. So, the question of bone conduction in that case I think is a very different one. Because you have parts of the skull which then make the contribution to the input to the cochlea. And the second comment is a semantic one. I'd like to ask everybody to avoid using the expression "Anything evolved to do something". Evolution is a blind process. There is no intention behind it at all. It may happen that at the end of this process, something is then possible. But that in general is simply an end-result. It is not as it were a designed process.

[Stefan Stenfelt] Thank you for those comments. As I said in the beginning, I don't know that much about evolution, so my disclaimer is that this has actually nothing to do with evolution, it just looking at what would these kinds of things imply. And I also realize that the cochlea was not evolutionary coiled in the human, it was in smaller mammals, I guess. So there are a lot of things in here that I don't really answer, I just looking at it from that perspective.